

DEVELOPMENT OF JOURNALISTIC EDUCATION IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8414421>

Due to the establishment and growth of the mass media in Karakalpakstan, it is clearly clear that there is a demand for journalists with advanced academic backgrounds and specialized training. The creation of a special department in 1949 at the Faculty of Philology of the Central Asian State University (now the National University of Uzbekistan) for the training of highly educated journalists and its separation into a separate faculty in 1967 [1-130] were important developments in the education of journalist specialists in Uzbekistan. This faculty of journalism played an important role in preparing the first journalists for the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Because over the years, a number of young people from Karakalpakstan studied at this institution, developed into successful journalists, and worked in our country's mass media.

For Karakalpak youth, however, traveling to Tashkent for an education was extremely difficult. This issue led to the development of special journalistic education in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the early 1980s and made journalism education a social need there.

We looked at the following stages in the evolution of journalism education and training in Karakalpakstan:

The stage of special journalism education formation. If we look at the history of journalism education in Karakalpakstan, we can see that the 1983–1984 academic year saw the beginning of the training of journalist experts at Nukus State University (now Karakalpak State University). The Faculty of Philology founded the "Journalism" department. Admission to higher education was briefly suspended from the following academic year through 1989, but it resumed this year. The faculty created the "Literary Theory and Journalism" department, which was led by professor K. Mambetov, a well-known author and doctor of philology. Students of journalism were successfully trained in the early years by philology professors S. Akhmetov, G. Esemuratov, K. Mambetov, A. Nazhimov, S. Sadykov, K. Allambergenov, I. Teo'liev, and others. The students also received the essential professional knowledge from seasoned specialists in the field, including Sh. Usnatdinov, M. Jumamuratova, Sh. Ayapov, R. Do'letmuratov, K. Reymov, and. Esbergenov, who graduated from the Faculty of Journalism of UzMU. This initiative is notable since it quickly trained the first local staff members with a specialized diploma for Karakalpakstani journalism.

A new stage of journalistic education. Along with all other fields, mass media growth received significant attention beginning in the early years of independence. A number of strategic activities have been carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has taken efforts to create a new democratic state and a free civil society, to establish and further develop a new, contemporary national journalism, to guarantee openness and transparency, and freedom of the mass media. The process of developing mature, thoroughly educated specialists in the subject has received considerable attention.

The creation of a separate "Journalism" department at Berdakh State University in Karakalpak in 1992 played a significant role in shaping the future of journalist specialist education in our country. The department of "Journalism" worked as a distinct department from 1999 to 2005 in accordance with Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decision No. 88 of February 26, 1999 "On Improving the System of Training and Retraining of Journalist Personnel". Professors Yu. Pakhratdinov, B. Abdikamalov, and Sh. Abdinazimov continue to lead the department and teach young journalists, together with associate professors M. Jumajuratov, B. Genjemuratov, Z. Kojiqbaeva, B. Palwanov, D. Bekbawliev, and Z. Orazymbetova dedicated attention to creating the pedagogical and teaching-methodological process in accordance with international norms.

The introduction of training for scientific and educational individuals in journalism was the primary characteristic and most successful part of this phase. About ten academics and educators have successfully defended their doctoral (later PhD and DSc) and candidacy theses in the recent years, laying the groundwork for the development of the necessary scientific and pedagogical staff in this sector. In addition, around 30 training manuals, monographs, and other works of literature written by the department's professors help to advance Karakalpak journalism's educational and methodological framework.

In conclusion, the establishment of a particular professional education program in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the 1980s that trained highly educated journalist specialists and its growth throughout the years served as a crucial basis for the growth of Karakalpakstan journalism.

This particular journalism education is now at a modern development stage. The primary concern at this time is to further enhance the teaching-methodical and pedagogical process and strengthen the material and technical base, while researching the experience of top international higher education institutions, in order to raise journalistic education to the level of global standards.

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